

1 Open data policy, e-commerce connectivity and catalog size 2 predict a global brand's online popularity rank 3

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 **Background**

13 Content marketing is increasingly important for online branding. Brand popularity can be more easily
14 determined online than sales-based measures but is not yet well-explained from a content marketing
15 perspective. Promising predictors are open data syndication policies, connectivity to e-commerce
16 platforms, product reviews, data health, and the depth and width of a brands product portfolio. A
17 predictive content marketing model can help brand owners to understand their e-commerce potential.

18

19 **Methods**

20 We used brand popularity (Brand Popularity Rank) and catalog data in combination with product
21 reviews from an independent content aggregator. For all datasets, we selected the overlapping dataset
22 for brand popularity and brand reviews based on a period of 90 days from June 10, 2022, till

23 September 24, 2022 (n = 333 brands). Backward stepwise multiple linear regression was used to
24 develop a predictive content marketing model of the Brand Popularity Rank.

25

26 **Results**

27 Through stepwise backward multiple linear regression five highly significant ($p < 0.01$) predictive
28 factors for brand rank are selected in our content marketing model: the brand's data syndication
29 policy, the number of connected e-commerce platforms, a brand's number of products, its number of
30 products per category, and the number of product categories in which it is active. Our model explains
31 78% of the variance of Brand Popularity Rank and has a good and highly significant fit: $F(5, 327) =$
32 $233.5, p < 0.00001$.

33

34 **Conclusions**

35 We conclude that a content marketing model can adequately predict a Brand Popularity Rank based on
36 online popularity. In this model an open content syndication policy, more connected e-commerce
37 platforms, and catalog size, i.e., presence in more categories and more products per category are each
38 related to a better (lower) Brand Popularity Rank score.

39 **Keywords**

40 Brand rank, content marketing, predictive model, open data policy, e-commerce

41 **Highlights**

- 42 • Brand Popularity Rank is a measure based on online product data-sheet downloads per brand.
- 43 • Brand Popularity Rank is improved when brands adopt an open content syndication policy, or
44 have more connections to e-commerce platforms, more products per category or presence in
45 more product categories.

- 46 • A content marketing model based on these predictors, explains 78% of the variance of the
47 Brand Popularity Rank.
- 48 • The added value of a brand's product review score or sustainability index as reliable
49 predictors in our model is not yet clear.

50

51 **1. Introduction**

52 Content marketing is becoming increasingly important for online branding, both business-to-business
53 (Bamm et al., 2018) and business-to-consumer. Sales based measures for consumer choices of brands
54 are in the online space often less accessible than brand popularity based measures (Kim et al., 2019).
55 Brand popularity is often estimated on the basis of product usage (Qian et al., 2022), but predicting it
56 is still a challenge.

57 Product reviews, product completeness and content syndication are all seen as important elements in
58 the content marketing mix contributing to brand popularity, especially for e-commerce. Online
59 reviews on product usage experiences are seen as an effective way to build a strong brand image,
60 which in turn helps to reduce consumer's buying uncertainty (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018). Further,
61 product completeness or data health is believed to influence consumer purchase decisions as well
62 (Amanah et al., 2018), although adding multimedia to complete product communication is only
63 helpful if it is used congruently (Hoogeveen, 1997). And, finally content syndication has become a
64 prominent element of content marketing in, for example, the publishing domain (Edo et al., 2019).
65 Content syndication policies can be "open" (Bruzzzone et al., 2020) or "exclusive" (Chang & Jhang,
66 2020).

67 Finally a brand's sustainability reporting (Loh & Tan, 2020) is increasingly seen as impactful
68 regarding corporate performance (Cowan & Guzman, 2020), and a clear relation between e-commerce
69 and sustainability is established (Reijnders & Hoogeveen, 2001).

70 Apart from evaluating the use of the brand popularity ranking as an indicator of brand popularity
71 instead of crude product usage metrics, the novelty of our research is based on the aim to almost fully
72 explain brand popularity from easily obtainable open data regarding a brand's online marketing mix.
73 We aim to do this by including key content marketing parameters in a single predictive model. In this
74 model, we include the recently identified content marketing variables such as data health or data
75 completeness, product reviews score, content syndication policy in addition to more classical factors
76 related to product usage and the depth and width of a brand's product catalog. The ability to predict a
77 brand's popularity based on easily obtainable open content marketing variables is a powerful and
78 modern tool for brand owners that want to understand their e-commerce potential. Regarding
79 modelling, we follow a similar statistical approach as we recently applied in the development of an
80 adequate predictive model for COVID-19 seasonality (Hoogeveen et al, 2022).

81

82 Our hypothesis is that a content marketing model, combining multiple digital marketing factors,
83 improves the prediction of the global popularity rank of a brand (Brand Popularity Rank) compared to
84 each factor alone. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to explore a comprehensive model to
85 improve the predictive modelling of a brand's global online popularity ranking.

86

87 **2. Methods**

88 **2.1 Data**

89 For the present analyses, we selected datasets for an initial sample of 500 brands, which is reduced to
90 333 brands ($n = 333$) by taking into account only the overlapping brands from each dataset.

91 For Brand Popularity Rank, we used the respective Iceat Rank dataset (2022) from June 10, 2022, till
92 September 24, 2022, and selected the top 500 brands. Icecat uses a standard method to recalculate a
93 brand's ranking on the basis of a brand's online product data-sheet downloads over the trailing 90
94 days. A Brand Popularity Rank of 1 is the best score, and a Brand Popularity Rank of 500 is the lowest

95 score in the dataset. As the open catalog is used by 10,000s of e-commerce companies over the world
96 on a daily basis for updating their own catalogs, it is seen as a sufficiently representative and extensive
97 statistical sample. Selected alternative online predictors for Brand Popularity Rank are the brands
98 review score, based on the Testseek reviews database, and further from the Icecat dataset are obtained:
99 data health score, product downloads, the number of user platforms, the syndication policy of a brand,
100 the number of products of a brand, and the number of categories in which a brand has at least 1
101 product. Additionally, we calculate the average number of products per category per brand.

102 The brand review score is calculated as the average of the review scores of all a brand's individual
103 products and results in a figure between 0 and 100% (or 0 and 1). There are for the selected brands 333
104 brands that have product reviews in the database to calculate the average score from. Data health is an
105 average based on the completeness of the product data-sheets which describe a brand's online
106 products. Product downloads is the number of times that a brand's products are downloaded by its e-
107 commerce platforms or end-users in the trailing 90 days. The number of user platforms are the number
108 of different e-commerce users that connect to the database to download product data-sheets of a brand
109 in the trailing 90 days. The syndication policy can be 'open', all of a brand's product data are made
110 available as open data, or 'closed', the brand's product data is only available for selected or authorized
111 e-commerce users.

112 The lack of standardized sustainability data makes it still hard to obtain a dataset with sufficient
113 coverage of the brands in our samples, so we could not include such a dataset in our present analysis.

114

115 **2.2 Data sets consolidation**

116 As said before, we selected for the brand ranking and reviews datasets the brands that were present in
117 both datasets in the overlapping period.

118 For sensitivity analyses, we extended the Brand Popularity Rank dataset to include all 500 brands,
119 initially selected. And, we perform multiple linear regression both with and without product data-sheet
120 downloads as predictor given that this variable is not truly independent as it is used to determine the

121 Brand Popularity Rank. Therefore, it is good test to see if our predictive model is sufficiently
122 powerful.

123 **2.3 Statistical analysis**

124 Variables are presented with their sample sizes (n), means (M), and standard deviations (SD). We
125 calculated correlation coefficients to assess the strength and direction of relations of each independent
126 variable with Brand Popularity Rank, and with each other.

127

128 Stepwise backward multiple linear regression for all independent variables on Brand Popularity Rank
129 was used to keep only candidate predictors that are significant ($p < 0.05$) in the model and remove
130 insignificant predictors. Next, we removed predictors that were multicollinear as defined below. With
131 the remaining independent variables the F-value, standard deviations and errors, degrees of freedom
132 (DF), and significance level, are calculated to test the goodness of fit hypothesis for our predictive
133 model for Brand Popularity Rank. Further, the multiple R, Multiple R squared (R^2) and adjusted R^2
134 correlation coefficients are calculated to estimate the predictive power of our model. Additionally, the
135 algebraic equation to predict Brand Popularity Rank is determined, which is just to be understood as
136 an empirical formula. Next, per independent variable the (standard) coefficient, t-stat and its 95% CI,
137 probability, and the variance inflation factor value (VIF) are calculated as well.

138 Further, as linear regression assumes normality of the residuals, we applied the Shapiro-Wilk test and
139 to test the homoscedasticity requirement – homogeneity of variance of residuals – the White test is
140 applied. To analyze multicollinearity we used an acceptable VIF value of 5 as a threshold, whereby we
141 see a VIF value below 2.5 as ideal. Additionally, the priori power is calculated of each predictor alone
142 and compared with the full model. Finally, we created calibration plots to visually review the fit of the
143 model.

144

145 For selected independent variables with a $p < 0.05$ and VIF score < 5 , standard \log_{10} , and square root
146 data transformations are applied to reduce non-linearity in relations between variables which helps to
147 reduce skewness, and, especially, meet the normality and homoscedasticity requirements. Such data
148 transformations do not change the nature and direction of relations between independent variables and
149 Brand Popularity Rank. As the variables in the datasets only contained positive numbers no further
150 data transformations were necessary.

151 We reported the results in APA style, adapted to journal requirements.

152 All statistical analyses were done with Stats Kingdom 2022, which we benchmarked on R version 3.5.

153

154 **3. Results**

155 **3.1 Variables and their correlations**

156 The sample sizes (N), means, and SDs of the independent variables as used in our multiple linear
157 regression models are summarized in Table 1. The values are given for the data sets after applied data
158 transformations.

159 The factors that inversely correlate (highly) significantly with Brand Popularity Rank (see Table 2),
160 are in order of strength: platforms, open data policy, categories, products, and reviews score. The
161 inverse correlations are logical as an improvement on these factors coincides with an improved, i.e.,
162 lower, Brand Popularity Rank. For example, an open data syndication policy, more connections to e-
163 commerce platforms, and a bigger catalog size (more products in more categories and more products
164 per category) lead to a better, i.e., lower, Brand Popularity Rank. The highly significant inverse
165 correlation with downloads speaks for itself given that Brand Popularity Rank is directly based on it.
166 Unsurprisingly, the same factors correlate (highly) significantly with downloads, except for reviews
167 score. Worth to highlight is that data health correlates highly significantly with review score ($r(500) =$
168 0.21 ($p < 0.00001$), especially given that these factors are fully independent measures.

169 After transformations and dataset restriction to brands with a review score, the correlations with Brand
 170 Popularity Rank are more or less the same. Only the correlation with products per category has
 171 become highly significant as well ($r(333) = -0.46, p < 0.00001$).

172 In both situations there are no collinears where independent variables have a correlation higher than r
 173 $= 0.8$ with each other.

174

175 **3.2 Outcomes predictive model**

176 After several iterations with stepwise backward multiple linear regression, five independent variables
 177 were selected from the combined pool of online marketing variables that are both significant ($p <$
 178 0.05) and have a VIF value below 5. These selected predictors are: open syndication policy, the
 179 number of connected e-commerce platforms, the number of products, the products/category and the
 180 number of categories in which a brand has products (see Table 3). In the total datasets, Data Health did
 181 not have a significant correlation with Brand Popularity Rank ($r(500) = 0.06, p = 0.23$) and was
 182 deselected for our model. Also, Product Reviews was deselected, despite a significant correlation with
 183 Brand Popularity Rank ($r(500) = -0.10, p = 0.022$) and given that it did not add explanatory power to
 184 our model.

185 On the basis of the multiple linear regression test, we can reject the null-hypothesis (H_0) that our
 186 combined predictive model with the five selected factors does not provide a good fit: $F_{(5, 327)} = 233.5, p$
 187 < 0.00001 . R^2 equals 0.781, which means that our predictors explain 78.1% of the variance of Brand
 188 Popularity Rank. The adjusted R square equals 0.778, and the coefficient of multiple correlation (R)
 189 equals 0.884 (see Fig. 1).

190 Below, the predictive content marketing model's regression formula for \widehat{GBR} :

$$191 \quad (51.7 - 7.25 \log_{10} C - 4.64 \log_{10} Pl - 2.47Po + 0.00727 \sqrt{Pr} - 7.40 \log_{10} PPC)^2$$

192 Where \widehat{GBR} is the predicted Brand Popularity Rank, C is the number of categories in which a brand
 193 has products, Pl is the number of e-commerce platforms that are downloading a brand's product data,

194 *Po* indicates whether a brand has an open data (“1”) syndication policy or an exclusive one (“0”), *Pr* is
195 the number of products that a brand has in total in its catalog, and *PPC* is the number of products that
196 a brand has per category in its catalog. *C*, *Pr*, and *PPC* are all variables describing the size (width and
197 depth) of a brand’s product portfolio.

198 Given the somewhat raised multicollinearity scores, *Products* has to be interpreted in our content
199 marketing model as a correction on *PPC*.

200 **3.3 Statistical outcomes sensitivity analyses**

201 As a sensitivity analysis we added downloads of a brand’s product data-sheets to the multiple linear
202 regression test. In effect, downloads replaces the products variable (see Table 4), the other predictors
203 and the outcomes are more or less the same: also on the basis of the second multiple linear regression
204 test, we can reject the H_0 that our predictive model with the five selected factors does not provide a
205 good fit: $F_{(5, 327)} = 225.2$, $p < 0.00001$, and R^2 equals 0.775, which means that our environmental
206 predictors explain 77.5% of the variance of Brand Popularity Rank. The adjusted R^2 equals 0.771, and
207 the coefficient of multiple correlation (R) equals 0.880. It means that there is again a very strong direct
208 and highly significant relation between our model’s predicted and the observed Brand Popularity
209 Rank. The outcomes are only slightly lower. The only difference is that the VIF scores are slightly
210 better (< 2.5).

211 Using downloads as a dependent variable instead of Brand Popularity Rank does not lead to
212 satisfactory outcomes because of concerns related to the homoscedasticity of residuals and normality
213 requirements. When including the whole dataset ($n = 500$ brands) despite having quite some missings
214 does lead to the inclusion of Review Score in the predictive model but again homoscedasticity or
215 normality requirements cannot be met.

216 **4. Discussion**

217 The predictive power of a combined content marketing model including a brands connected platforms,
218 its content syndication policy, the number of products, products per category and the number of
219 categories in which it is active is good (77.4%). For example, an open syndication policy, more

220 connected e-commerce platforms, and more products per category and more categories in which a
221 brand is active, are related to a better (lower) Brand Popularity Rank score. The number of products
222 can be seen as a correction on the product per category variable in our model.

223 When we test our model by including the number of downloads these products generate as
224 *independent* variable, the predictive power of our model remains more or less the same. Given that the
225 downloads factor was used to determine the Brand Popularity Rank, it implies that our content
226 marketing model contains a robust – equally powerful - set of independent predictors. The
227 transformation of downloads into Brand Productivity Rank is superior to other transformations in the
228 sense that homoscedasticity and normality requirements are fully met, which is not the case when
229 downloads is used as *dependent* variable instead of Brand Productivity Rank.

230

231 Assuming that the same online marketing factors are relevant as predictors for brands outside our
232 sample, we hypothesize that our model has a similar predictive power for brands in other sectors or
233 categories outside our sample.

234 *Methodological concerns*

235 The Brand Popularity Rank panel is relatively strong in Western countries, which might lead to a
236 sampling bias. It would be interesting to see if the derived predictive content marketing model would
237 fundamentally change if the panel is strengthened in East-Asian and African countries.

238 Further, it would of interest to see the completeness of the product reviews dataset in terms of brand
239 coverage being improved. It might lead to the inclusion of product reviews score as a significant
240 predictor, as shown in a sensitivity analysis, leading to a slightly improved predictive power of our
241 model.

242 Finally, it would still be of interest to see if a brand's sustainability score can be obtained with
243 sufficient coverage of our brands sample, and whether its inclusion has added value for the predictive
244 model.

245 **Conclusion**

246 Our predictive content marketing model explains 78.1% of the variance of Brand Popularity Rank, and
247 provides a very good fit $F_{(5, 327)} = 233.5$, $p < 0.00001$, as the predicted and observed Brand Popularity
248 Rank correlate strongly and highly significantly. The significant predictors in the combined model are
249 a brand's content syndication policy, the number of connect e-commerce platforms, a brand's number
250 of products, products per category and the number of categories in which it is active. The mentioned
251 factors are inversely correlated with Brand Popularity Rank, i.e., an open syndication policy, more
252 connected e-commerce platforms, more products per category and being active in more categories all
253 lead to a better (lower) Brand Popularity Rank. In our model, the number of products, another attribute
254 of a brand's catalog size, should be seen as a correction on the product per category variable.

255 Using Brand Popularity Rank as a dependent variable leads to more statistically robust models than
256 when product data-sheet downloads is used a brand popularity indicator.

257 It is yet to be determined whether a brand's product review or sustainability score have added value
258 for a predictive content marketing model, due to the lack of standardized values per matching brand.

259

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298

299 **FIGURES AND TABLES**300 **Table 1: overview means (M), standard deviations (SDs) and skewness values**

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Downloads	333	9,237,924	3,130,1091
Log ₁₀ (Platforms)	333	1.83	0.46
Open data policy	333	0.46	0.50
Log ₁₀ (Products/category)	333	2.10	0.61
Log ₁₀ (Categories)	333	1.85	0.38
Temperature ²	333	221	142
Dew point temperature	333	8.56	5.70
Sqrt(Products)	333	130	155
Sqrt(Brand Popularity Rank)	333	14.0	5.37

301 *Table 1: Overview of mean (M), and standard deviation (SD) per independent variable as used in the*
302 *multiple linear regression models. The function Sqrt returns the square root of the variable.*

303

304

	Brand Popularity Rank	Data Health	Downloads	Platforms	Review score	Open data policy	Products	Categories	PPC
Brand Popularity Rank	1.000	0.054	<u>-0.351</u>	<u>-0.538</u>	<u>-0.102</u>	<u>0.321</u>	<u>-0.261</u>	<u>-0.320</u>	-0.047
Data Health	0.054	1.000	-0.029	-0.035	<u>0.207</u>	0.060	-0.002	-0.064	<u>-0.112</u>
Downloads	<u>-0.351</u>	-0.029	1.000	<u>0.669</u>	0.018	<u>0.176</u>	<u>0.648</u>	<u>0.432</u>	0.038
Platforms	<u>-0.538</u>	-0.035	<u>0.669</u>	1.000	0.075	<u>0.522</u>	<u>0.313</u>	<u>0.438</u>	-0.067
Reviews score	<u>-0.102</u>	<u>0.207</u>	0.018	0.075	1.000	0.045	0.033	<u>-0.090</u>	0.054
Open data policy	<u>-0.321</u>	-0.060	<u>0.176</u>	<u>0.522</u>	<u>0.045</u>	1.000	-0.012	0.070	-0.084
Products	<u>-0.261</u>	-0.002	<u>0.648</u>	<u>0.313</u>	0.033	0.012	1.000	<u>0.225</u>	<u>0.297</u>
Categories	<u>-0.320</u>	-0.064	<u>0.432</u>	<u>0.438</u>	<u>-0.090</u>	0.070	<u>0.225</u>	1.000	<u>-0.104</u>
Products/Category	-0.047	<u>-0.112</u>	0.038	-0.067	0.054	0.084	<u>0.297</u>	<u>-0.104</u>	1.000

305

306 *Table 2: Overview of correlations between variables before transformations and limitations of the*307 *dataset (n = 500). Bold: significant at p < 0.05. Bold+Underlined: highly significant at p < 0.01*

308

309 **Table 3: multiple linear regression for predictors excluding downloads**

	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t-stat</i>	<i>lower</i> <i>t0.025(327)</i>	<i>upper</i> <i>t0.975(327)</i>	<i>Stand. Coeff.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>VIF</i>
<i>b</i>	51.7	1.63	31.6	48.5	54.9	0	<0.00001	
<i>Log₁₀(Categories)</i>	-7.26	0.55	-13.2	-8.34	-6.18	-0.51	<0.00001	2.20
<i>Log₁₀(Platforms)</i>	-4.64	0.42	-11.2	-5.45	-3.82	-0.40	<0.00001	1.91
<i>Open data policy</i>	-2.47	0.35	-7.14	-3.16	-1.79	-0.23	<0.00001	1.55
<i>Sqrt(Products)</i>	0.00727	0.00166	4.37	0.00399	0.0105	0.209	0.000017	3.44
<i>Log₁₀(Products/Category)</i>	-7.40	0.42	-17.5	-8.23	-6.57	-0.84	<0.00001	3.43

310 *Table 3: Overview of outcomes per predictor after multiple linear regression without downloads*311 *resulting in an adjusted R-squared = 0.778. Selection of predictors is based on being (highly)*

312 *significant and having multicollinearity (VIF) score below 5. The function Sqrt returns the square root*
 313 *of the variable.*

314

315 **Table 4: multiple linear regression for all predictors including downloads**

316

	Coeff.	SE	t-stat	lower t_{0.025(327)}	upper t_{0.975(327)}	Stand. Coeff.	P	VIF
b	48.6	1.33	36.6	46.0	51.3	0	<0.00001	
Downloads	1.79e-8	5.87e-9	3.06	6.40e-9	2.95e-8	0.105	0.00241	1.70
Log ₁₀ (Platforms)	-4.65	0.428	-10.9	-5.49	-3.81	-0.400	<0.00001	1.96
Open data policy	-2.55	0.352	-7.24	-3.25	-1.86	-0.237	<0.00001	1.56
Log ₁₀ (Products/category)	-6.35	0.288	-22.0	-6.92	-5.78	-0.720	<0.00001	1.55
Log ₁₀ (Categories)	-6.35	-0.478	-13.3	-7.29	-5.41	-0.444	<0.00001	1.62

317 *Table 4: Overview of outcomes for selected predictors including downloads after multiple linear*
 318 *regression resulting in an adjusted R-squared = 0.771. Selection of predictors is based on being*
 319 *(highly) significant and having multicollinearity (VIF) score below 5.*

320

321

322

Figure 1: scatter diagram predicted versus observed reproduction number

323

324 *Fig. 1: The predictive content marketing model is explaining 78.1% of the variance of the observed*
325 *Brand Popularity Rank.*

326

327 FOOTNOTES PAGE

328 **Martijn Hoogeveen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing,
329 Investigation, Visualization, Resources.

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332 not-for-profit sectors.

333 Declarations of interest

334 Corresponding other is founder of data science bureau Icecat, the provider of the used open data set
335 regarding Brand Popularity Rank. But, there is no conflict of interest regarding any potential outcome
336 of the data science project reported in this manuscript.

337 **Data statement**

338 The links to downloadable datasets are provided in the reference list or references to the sources are
339 included. Upon request, the data used for this manuscript is available for inspection, but for other
340 purposes we kindly refer to the respective copyright-holder(s).

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